

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6628927

THE USE OF MODERN DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN SPORTS AND SPORTS MEDICINE

Alexander Egoyan - Associate Professor, Doctor of Physics and Mathematics;

Email: alexegoyan@gmail.com ;

Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport, Tbilisi, Georgia.

Elena Tyo - Doctor of Public Administration candidate;

Academy of Public Administration under the President of Kazakhstan, Almaty, Kazakhstan.

Sabina Shakhverdieva - MBA International;

Athens University of Economics and Business, Athens, Greece.

Alexander Gobirakhashvili – Associate Professor, Doctor of Pedagogics;

Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport, Tbilisi, Georgia.

Ilia Khipashvili - Teacher, Honoured Coach of Georgia, Georgian State College of Physical Education and Sport, Tbilisi, Georgia.

Karlo Moistsrapishvili – Professor, Doctor of Physics and Mathematics;

Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport, Tbilisi, Georgia.

Abstract. In our work, we discuss the possibilities of modern digital technologies and perspectives of their use in sports and sports medicine. The ways of integration of computational approaches such as artificial intelligence, expert systems, virtual reality and cloud computing with sensors, mobile technology, high-speed digital video cameras and wireless networks are considered. It is shown that the abovementioned methods and technologies allow us to obtain more reliable data about sportsmen's physical and physiological parameters, giving us the possibility to optimize the training process and improve the quality of trauma prediction and rehabilitation.

Keywords: Sport, sports digitalization, sensors, motion analysis, expert systems, virtual reality.

Introduction

The growing importance of information gathering and processing methods in the modern world is equally evident in the various fields of sport, which in turn can be used for a deeper knowledge and understanding of sport [1]. Computers allow to create mathematical and biomechanical models of various sports movements, calculate the trajectories of sports tools, and evaluate the visual and auditory reactions of an athlete [2-4].

Researchers at the University of Tennessee use computers to estimate and improve hand and eye response time to reduce the risk of injury and prevent trauma [6].

In recent years, computer technology has developed exponentially: artificial intelligence, cloud computing, mobile technology, GPS navigation devices, wireless networks, virtual reality, and the Internet of Things have gradually changed the face of the modern world.

There is no doubt that these technologies open a new horizon for sports researchers and sports professionals.

Therefore, the study and introduction of modern computer technologies is very relevant.

Materials and methods

This article discusses aspects of using modern computer technologies in sports. The complex use of computer technology in sports with the participation of specialists in various fields is also discussed. The main purpose of the research is to summarize the materials presented in the

scientific literature. In addition, special attention is paid to the computer methods created at the Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sports.

Results and Discussion

Proceeding from the detailed analysis of scientific literature we can distinguish the following main areas of the use of computer technology in sports and sports medicine:

Information collection technologies, databases, and expert systems. The larger the amount of data to be processed, the more difficult it is to perform appropriate analysis and evaluation. Expert systems, or programs that use existing knowledge bases and inference mechanisms to solve problems, are among the methods that can help the coach or physical medicine specialist. Scientists believe that neural networks can be a useful tool for predicting sports injury when the connection between biomechanical analysis results and real injury data is very difficult. Thanks to AI, great success has been achieved in the analysis of video recordings of body movements. Much of the analysis of captured videos can be automated, so quantitative assessment of gait and other human movement defects is done automatically.

Measurements, connected objects and Internet of Things (IoT). In general, there are two types of connected objects in the IoT domain: general-purpose connected objects (such as smartwatches and activity trackers) and specialized connected objects (such as pedals, rockets, and balls). The IoT allows us to control the athlete's physiological and physical parameters while exercising remotely. The use of IoT in the field of healthcare includes several different areas: physiological monitoring, creating better conditions for the patient, and well-being tasks. Various types of sensors designed in the field of rehabilitation are used to monitor the feedback of the physical therapy process and the correctness of the exercises performed. IoT can also be used to control sports equipment: for example, to determine and analyze the trajectory of the ball remotely. In sports, remote control of the athlete and sports equipment is needed to optimize the training process, and in rehabilitation, monitoring of the patient's physiological and physical condition is very important if the patient needs constant monitoring.

Statistical methods. Methods of statistical analysis may be very useful for obtaining time dependencies of sportsmen's physical and physiological parameters.

Statistical analysis allows us to predict the possible outcome of matches based on the analysis of various factors, such as what form the team is in, how the field factor affects the team, how the team played the previous matches against the opponent, and so on. Statistical analysis can also be used to determine the optimal physiological and anthropometric parameters of athletes representing different sports.

Motion analysis systems. Motion analysis methods can be divided into optical and non-optical methods. Optical systems require special markers to be placed on the sportsman's or patient's body and use digital video cameras. Non-optical systems are sensor-based and include inertial, magnetic, and mechanical motion analysis techniques. In this case, the subject of the study is wearing a special costume that contains sensors. Traditionally, movement analysis of professional athletes has been conducted in a laboratory setting. Advances in microelectronics and other micro-technologies have made it possible to monitor and analyse the movements of elite athletes in their natural training environment. Of particular interest is the integration of motion analysis systems with other physiological research methods such as electromyography and electroencephalography, as well as devices such as force platforms, bicycle ergometers and treadmills. Also of some interest are motion analysis systems that work without sensors and markers. Such a system has been developed and implemented in the Georgian State Teaching

University of Physical Culture and Sports. The program is based on the kinematic model of the athlete's body and allows us to determine the trajectories of the centres of gravity of the joints and major parts of the athlete's body and improve his or her feeling of equilibrium [5].

Computer modelling. Mathematical modelling makes it possible to calculate the trajectory of the ball taking into account the atmospheric influence, evaluate the dependence of the final result on the proportions of the athlete's body, and analyse the physiological reaction of the athlete to the exercises. By means of computer modelling, a special calculator has been created at the Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sports to assess the impact of wind, altitude and temperature on sports performance. The program includes 100-meter sprints, long jumps and jumps [2]. The program can be useful for determining how effectively an athlete is using his potential in the current weather conditions.

Simulators and Virtual Reality (VR). Many professional teams in the NFL, NBA and NCAA have already incorporated VR into their training process. In sports such as baseball, basketball, and tennis, athletes can train in the virtual world and refine their techniques in response to computer system feedback. VR technology gives coaches the ability to observe athletes from different angles to better understand their behaviour, while athletes can also watch their games in the virtual world. VR allows coaches to train athletes' minds without affecting their bodies. Researchers at the Georgian State University of Physical Education and Sports have developed a soccer ball trajectory simulator taking into account such factors as the moment of rotation, altitude, wind, temperature and more [3]. The simulator can be used for educational purposes and for simulation of his own shots, taking into account personal parameters (ball speed, torque, shot angle, etc.). Virtual reality therapy uses specially programmed computers, optical immersion devices, and artificially created environments to evoke in the patient a simulated feeling that is used to diagnose and treat his or her psychological state.

Video games. As for computer games, it should be mentioned that according to scientific studies, playing video games on the computer for 10-15 minutes a day is beneficial for athletes. Modern computer games are created with the participation of sports experts, so they can help athletes learn additional technical and tactical tricks. Researchers at the Georgian State University of Physical Education and Sports have created a computer program that contains video game elements and allows us to determine the speed of reaction of athletes in different directions and their ability to concentrate for a relatively long time [4]. The program can also be used to improve reaction and concentration. In case of visual reaction, interfaces have been developed for sports such as football, basketball, rugby and handball. Applications have also been developed to assess and improve the auditory response, which are mainly used by the Georgian Blind Football National Team.

Multimedia and educational software. Multimedia and computer programs such as the "Tactical Pad" or "Open Sim" not only create a good learning environment for students, but can also effectively reduce learning time. The use of such programs is very important to improve the quality and effectiveness of training and to achieve the best learning goals.

Conclusion

In turn, computer specialists and technicians will become better acquainted with new technologies and methods. All these areas of computer technology are of interest to professionals in various fields of sports science. As a result of joint activities, specialists of different qualifications can expand their knowledge and skills. Coaches can enrich their knowledge in the

fields of sports physiology, biomechanics and psychology, while doctors and psychologists can improve their knowledge in the field of sports.

Computer technology can help us achieve the following goals:

1. Optimization of the training process;
2. Improving the qualification of athletes;
3. Predict the results of future matches and other sporting events;
4. Reduce the risk of injury;
5. Develop more effective post-traumatic rehabilitation strategies for athletes;
6. Promoting sports and attracting more people to it;
7. Increase the visibility of the learning process.

The future use of computers in sports will be based on technologies such as sensors, GPS, wireless networks and sophisticated software, where expert systems, cloud computing and new algorithms for 3D modelling and data integration from sensors will be widely implemented.

Our analysis has shown that the use of computer technology has great prospects in sports. Athletes, researchers in various fields of science and computer technology specialists should join forces to develop a consistent methodology for the use of new computer methods and integrated techniques.

References

1. Dabnichki P., Baca A., Brebbia C. A. Computers in sport, WITpress, 2008, pp. 352.
2. Egoyan A., Gobirakhashvili A. Computer modeling of the impact of atmospheric effects on sports results in athletics. The scientific conference for professors and teachers of the Faculty of Coaching of the Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport "Modern Sport and its Problems", 28-29 April 2020.
3. Egoyan A. E., Khipashvili I. A., Moistsrapishvili K. M. A 3D computer simulator to examine the effect of wind and altitude on a soccer ball trajectory, Physical Education, Sport and Science (PSS), 2017, 3: 8-18. DOI: 10.21846/TST.2017.4.1
4. Egoyan A. E., Khipashvili I. A. Use of psychophysiological computer tests during the process of sportsmen's preparation, Physical Education, Sport and Science (PSS), 2017, 3: 8-17. DOI:10.21846/TST.2017.3.1
5. Moistsrapishvili K. M., Egoyan A. E. Computer modelling of the equilibrium of a sportsman's body for improving sports results, XXII International scientific congress «Olympic sport and sport for all», Tbilisi, Georgia, 2018, 74-78.
6. Wilkerson G. B., Simpson K. A., Clark R. A. Assessment and training of visuomotor reaction time for football injury prevention, J Sport Rehabil., 2017, 26(1), 26-34.